

and complexes indicates that N-H frequency remains unchanged in the complexes. The decrease in stretching³⁻⁵ frequency from about 720-730 cm⁻¹ in the ligands to 630-640 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicates M-S bonding. The presence of new bands at about 500 cm⁻¹ and 450 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicate the coordination through N and S. The presence of the bands at 830 cm⁻¹ and 1380 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of uncoordinated nitrite group⁶. It was not possible to get any information regarding the co-ordination of chlorine as I.R. spectra were recorded between 4000 cm⁻¹ and 400 cm⁻¹ only.

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Semi-Micro Titrimetric Estimation of Silver(I) Using N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-Cysteine*

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SILVER can be estimated by a number of titrimetric methods^{1,2} involving precipitation, complexation, etc. All these are based on the low solubilities of silver halides and/or pseudohalides. Some of these methods require accurate control of proper pH values particularly for the action of the indicators used. The present communication describes a method in which silver has been estimated on the semi-micro scale by acid-base titration using the ligand N-Benzenesulphonyl-L-Cysteine [NBSC or

C₆H₅SO₂NHCH(COOH)CH₂SH or HS-LH-COOH]. The amount of alkali required to titrate silver(I) solution containing some free mineral acid using phenol-red indicator represents the total amount of free acid only. When a solution of mono-sodium salt of the ligand, HSLHCOONa, is added providing sufficient excess to this titrated solution one equivalent of acid per gram-atom of silver is liberated due to deprotonation the thiol (-SH) group of the ligand by silver(I) according to the stoichiometry:

Titration with alkali is continued and the amount of alkali required at this stage to reach a just red end point gives the amount of silver(I) present. The amount of silver was calculated using the factor 1 ml of (N) NaOH solution \equiv 107.9 mg of Ag.

Experimental

(a) Reagent Solution:

A 2% solution of monosodium salt (HSLHCOONa) of NBSC was used as the reagent. This was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of the ligand NBSC^{2,3} in water and neutralising the solution with carbonate-free NaOH using phenol red indicator^{1,2}. 10-15 ml of this solution was used for each titration of 6-60 mg of silver.

(b) Procedure:

Aliquots (containing 6-60 mg of silver) of a standard AgClO₄ solution were diluted nearly to 100 ml and phenol red indicator^{1,2} (3 drops) was added and the resulting solution was titrated with a carbonate free standard (\approx 0.30 M) sodium hydroxide solution to a just red colour. The amount of alkali required was equivalent to the amount of free mineral acid present in the AgClO₄ solution. 10-15 ml of the reagent solution was then added. Colour of the solution changed to yellow and a white solid, AgSLHCOOH, (confirmed by analysis and i.r. study on isolation) was precipitated. Titration with alkali was continued, the solid compound redissolved during the course of titration. Amount of alkali required at this stage to get a just-red end point gave the amount of silver present in the solution. The results of the estimations are recorded in Table I.

(c) Interferences:

Substances which oxidise the ligand and/or reduce Ag(I) interfere. Metal ions such as Hg(II), Cd(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(II), Bi(III), Pb(II), Pt(II), Pd(II), which form complexes with the ligand and Fe(III), Al(III) of which hydroxides are precipitated below or within the experimental pH range interfere. Fe(III) up to 15% can be

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TABLE 1—RESULTS OF TITRIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF SILVER; STRENGTH OF SILVER PERCHLORATE SOLUTION: [Ag]=3.054 mg/ml.; FREE MINERAL ACID=0.02080M; STRENGTH OF TITRANT NaOH=0.08927M

Ag taken (mg) ^a	Strength of free acid found (M)	Ag found (mg)	Relative Error (%)
61.08	0.02088	60.94	-0.23
45.81	0.02085	45.68	-0.28
30.54	0.02088	30.54	nil
24.43	0.02089	24.43	nil
15.27	0.02080	15.27	nil
9.16	0.02080	9.24	+0.87
6.11	0.02080	6.19	+1.31

tolerated by masking with potassium fluoride (neutralized using phenol red indicator). Interference by Pb(II) could not be eliminated by precipitation of sulphate as because precipitated PbSO₄ slowly reacts with the reagent solution. Ag(I) has to be estimated after separating it from all these metal ions by usual procedures.

The relative standard deviation in the estimation of silver was ± 0.091 . 60-6 mg of silver were estimated with a relative error of $\approx 1.4\%$.

Discussion

The silver compound, AgSLHCOOH, has been isolated and confirmed by elemental analysis (Found: Ag, 29.38; N, 3.78%; Calc. Ag, 29.35; N, 3.80%). IR study on the ligand, HSLHCOOH and the silver compound, AgSLHCOOH confirmed that the later compound was formed by the deprotonation of the thiol (-SH) group of the ligand. The characteristic bands for -COOH (1735-1740 cm⁻¹) and -SO₂NH- (1335-1340 cm⁻¹ and 1165 cm⁻¹) were found present both in the ligand and in the silver compound while that for the -SH group (2597 cm⁻¹) was present in the ligand but it was absent in the silver compound. Thus the method involves the titration of the acid liberated due to deprotonation of the -SH group of the ligand by Ag⁺ ions. Obviously the protons displaced get bonded to the COO⁻ groups of HSLHCOO⁻ and/or AgSLHCOO⁻. Hence, the equivalence point pH is governed by the ions HSLHCOO⁻ and AgSLHCOO⁻. The pK_{COOH} (3.16) and pK_{SH} (10.32) of the ligand, HSLHCOOH and pK_{COOH} (4.56) and pK_{NH} (10.48) of the silver compound, AgSLHCOOH, in aqueous solution [ionic strength, $\mu=0.5(\text{NaClO}_4)$, temperature $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$], reveal that pH of the solution containing the ions HSLHCOO⁻ and AgSLHCOO⁻ will be nearly 6.8~7.6 and consequently phenol red having its colour change interval from pH 6.8 to 8.0^{1b} is a suitable indicator for this purpose.

The free mineral acid in the Ag(I) solution has to be neutralised using the same indicator (phenol red) before the addition of reagent solution, keeping the silver ion concentration 0.01M or lower.

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Studies on the Suppression of Polarographic Maximum of Ni(II) by Na(I), Sr(II), Ba(II), Ca(II) and Al(III) vis-a-vis their Influence on the Kinetics of Electrode Reaction

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HEYROVSKY¹, Lal and Srivastava²⁻³ have reported order of effectiveness of some cations in the suppression of the maxima of Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II) and Pb(II). But all these studies are qualitative in nature in as much as that they describe the influence of increasing concentrations of the cations on the height and position of the maximum. Recently, Singh and co-workers⁴ have attempted the suppression of Ni(II) maximum by some heavy metal cations and also studied the kinetics of the electrode reaction of Ni(II) as a function of concentration of the heavy metal cation from the stage where the maximum just disappears. In present study an attempt has been made to suppress the maximum of Ni(II) by some Uni-, Bi- and Tri-valent cations and then compare the efficacies of different valent cations quantitatively, in term of the kinetic parameter, ' αn_a '.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of BDH AnalaR grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The depolarizer concentration was kept at $2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$. 0.1 M Sodium Nitrate was used as a supporting electrolyte.

A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CLO2) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal

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